

Original Research

Behaviour recommendations with a deep learning model and genetic algorithm for health debt characterisation

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ABSTRACT

Human behaviour is a dense longitudinal multi-featured measure that directly impacts the health of individuals in the short and long terms. Therefore, issues usually emerge from the insistence on performing risky behaviours, such as smoking or eating fast foods, which continuously increase the gap between current and beneficial health states. This paper introduces the term “health debt” as an economic metaphor to represent the quantification of this gap in domains such as sleep, contributing to physical and mental health states. Then, we present a theoretical framework that relies on behaviour change recommendations to quantify this debt. The practical instantiation of this framework relies on passively assessed sleep related data via personal wearable devices, and uses of an attention-based predictive model as the fitness function of a genetic algorithm that acts as a recommender. We evaluate this proposal by means of a case example aimed at improving the sleep duration of individuals. Results show, for example, that the use of individual rather than generic datasets produces more accurate models. At the same time, the use of constraints on the variability of behaviours features generates more feasible recommendations. These foundations open new research opportunities to support the adoption of preventive medicine based on longitudinal wearable passive data analysis.

1. Introduction

Behaviour can be defined as the internally coordinated responses (actions or inactions) of whole living organisms (individuals or groups) to internal and/or external stimuli, excluding responses more easily understood as developmental changes (e.g., aging) [1]. Previous research shows that daily life, repetitive harmful behaviours contribute to the deterioration of human health. For example, Gillison et al. [2] emphasises that much of the potential for reducing the world’s disease burden lies in changing people’s health behaviours. Other studies [3] corroborate such an assertion, arguing that “lifestyle behaviours such as diet and physical activity are implicated in the development of disease states such as obesity, Type 2 diabetes, and metabolic syndrome, and changing these health behaviours can have as powerful effect on health and wellbeing outcomes as the best available medical interventions”.

Indeed, individuals that have a poor diet, avoid the practice of physical exercises, and/or are frequently exposed to stressful situations tend to create a health debt and continuously increase such debt. As indicated in the semantics of the term debt in economics, if this debt is not paid (e.g., behaviour changing towards more beneficial practices), it

will incur cumulative interests until triggering severe health issues. Thus, as later someone tries to pay this debt, the harder the process is to return to a healthy state. The challenge in this domain is how to quantify and, mainly, recommend behaviour changes that could attenuate or ever avoid the evolution of this debt.

As human behaviour is a dense, longitudinal, and multifeatured measure [4], newly researched computational systems in health care shall not ignore the sequence of users’ behaviours when the aim is to predict or anticipate potential health issues and recommend beneficial behaviour changes. In other words, these emerging computational systems require models that capture the dependencies between temporal parts of sequential behaviour data. Consider a health prediction model $M(\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_n) \rightarrow y$, where β_1 to β_n represent the sequence of n behaviours, and y is a prediction variable reflecting a health outcome (e.g., depression status). Given this model M , we can generate different q values for the last behaviour β_n (e.g., $\beta_n^1, \beta_n^2, \dots, \beta_n^q$) and obtain different results y^1, y^2, \dots, y^q . Therefore, β_n^k , where $k \in [1..q]$, is a potential recommendation for behaviour change if the value of y^k improves, regarding values associated with previous behaviours.

This paper firstly aims to analyse deep learning architectures that are a candidate to generate longitudinal models similar to M . An important

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Nomenclature

Symbol	Description
β_i	Behaviour (set of features) at the time i
$\beta_{i,j}$	Specific feature j that composes a behaviour β at the time i
y	Prediction variable specified for a learning task (e.g., sleep duration)
$[1..n]$	Temporal interval of assessed behaviours, where a time $i \in [1..n]$
$[n + 1..m]$	Temporal interval of recommended behaviours, where a time $i \in [n + 1..m]$
$V\beta$	Vector of behaviours assessed
$V\beta'$	Vector of behaviours recommended
$V\mu(\beta)$	Vector of average values μ for each feature that composes β
γ	Standard deviation of mutation, which controls the Gauss distribution for the generation of new genes when mutations occur
α	Mutation rate, which indicates how many genes (features) may be modified
β^g	Behaviour generated by the recommender

requirement of this research is to use simple architectures since the technologies developed in our research lab are supposed to run on limited platforms (e.g., wearables). This premise is also important considering the current mobile technological trend in assessing passive data and monitoring human behaviours [5,6]. Then, several architectures are discussed, including the use of the recent attention mechanism [7]. Secondly, we analyse the accuracy of the generated models also considering different dataset configurations. Finally, the architecture and configuration presenting the most accurate results were used to implement M , which acts as the fitness function of a genetic algorithm that optimises the generation of recommendations (β_n^k), also supporting their explanations.

2. Material and methods

This section initially summarises the background of the architectures that could be used to implement the model M , and the principles of the genetic algorithm used as recommendation generator. Then, it characterises the concept of health debt and its constructors, and discusses the proposed framework, detailing its components. The symbols and notations used in this section are summarised as an appendix at the end of this paper.

2.1. Background

The current literature provides diverse architectures that are a candidate to generate the behaviour model M [8,9,11]. These architectures mainly implement three learning mechanisms (recurrence, convolution, and attention) over the processing of multifeatured dense longitudinal data. Therefore, we selected architectures for a comparative analysis representing these different learning mechanisms.

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks were used to represent the recurrent architectures. While they are more complex than the traditional recurrent neural networks (RNNs) [8], LSTM still provides a tractable solution to deal with longitudinal data. This feature is demonstrated in the work of Guo et al. [9], which used LSTM models to predict future cardiovascular health levels based on previous measurements from longitudinal electronic health record (EHR) data. The authors also show that LSTM architectures (e.g., Vanilla LSTM, 2-Stacked LSTM, and Bidirectional LSTM) provide better accuracy than other

approaches such as Logistic Regression and Random Forest. Moreover, LSTMs attenuate the vanishing gradient problem, which is a typical problem of architectures that use recurrence to cover long data sequences.

While recurrent architectures are the common choice for longitudinal data processing, we also included Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in our analysis. According to [10], although CNN is mostly applied for analysing images, it is also successfully explored in longitudinal data since multivariate time series have the same 2-dimensional data structures as images. For example, Zhao et al. [11] discuss the advantages of CNN in improving cardiovascular event prediction, comparing its efficiency with other approaches. However, different from its use for image analysis, which uses the 2-dimensional CNN (Conv2D) approach, the analysis of longitudinal data is based on 1-dimensional CNN (Conv1D), where the kernel slides along only one dimension (temporal dimension).

The hybrid CNN-LSTM architecture is another approach recently used for multifeatured longitudinal health analysis. This approach uses CNN to interpret sub-sequences of inputs that together are provided as a sequence to an LSTM model to interpret. The work in [12], for example, shows that CNN-LSTM models present better results when compared to pure CNN and LSTM implementations.

Finally, we have included the Temporal Pattern Attention (TPA) architecture [20] as the representative of the attention-based learning strategy. The attention mechanism [7] allows the processing of entire sequences in parallel, scaling the speed and capacity of such processing compared to recurrent approaches. Moreover, this mechanism considers the relationship between features, irrespective of where they are placed in a sequence. Thus, it allows tracking relations between features across long sequences in both forward and reverse directions. The work of Shih et al. [20] shows that its adaptation of the attention mechanism achieves state-of-the-art performance compared to other approaches that use the same learning strategy.

The identification of an adequate architecture is important since it will define the model used as the fitness function of a recommender, implemented as a genetic algorithm (GA) [13]. GA is an optimization process based on survival, where the best solutions evolve while the weakest ones are eliminated. This optimization involves a stochastic search of the solution space using data structures, known as chromosomes, which contain the features (genes) being jointly optimised. GA performs in cycles after creating an initial population of chromosomes. At each cycle (generation), chromosomes are subjected to operations involving selection, crossover, and mutation. Selection involves retaining the best chromosomes for the next population, according to their fitness values. The other chromosomes are replaced by new chromosomes formed through crossover and mutation processes. Crossover is a process in which two chromosomes from the current generation (parent chromosomes) engage in a procedure in which some genes from one chromosome are interchanged with genes from the corresponding positions in the other. Mutation involves the random selection of a certain number of genes in the current population, and random alterations are then made to their values. These operations are carried out at each cycle until a stop condition is reached.

The use of GA is justified since it allows a weak coupling with the prediction module. This low interdependence degree facilitates modifications in the prediction module, which do not affect the generation of recommendations. GAs also use payoff (objective function) information rather than derivatives that demand more computational power. Moreover, GAs are adequate for our “noisy” domain (noisy because it relies on *in the wild* assessments) since they search from a population of solutions rather than a simple solution. Therefore, GAs can generate diverse recommendations, while the model M predicts (rates) the effect of such recommendations. After that, the genetic operations of selection, crossover, and mutation ensure that the population of recommendations tends to improve at each new cycle. To the best of our knowledge, this form of integration between a prediction model and a GA is new in the

recommendation systems literature, which mostly explores the genetic algorithms for computing similarities between users. A review on the use of genetic algorithms in recommendation systems can be seen in [13].

2.2. Health debt characterisation

Debt is like an obligation that requires someone acts in some sense to finish this obligation. The most common use of this term is in the economic area, where debt is a sum of money owed or due. However, its semantics adequately represent the “obligation to act” in several other domains. For example, the software engineering area uses the term “technical debt” [14] as a form to express the negative effects of postponing appropriate project decisions by looking for momentary advantages (e.g., budget reduction or early software release). Thus, when a debt is created, the longer adequate changes are conducted (the debt is not paid), the harder the implementation of such changes is.

Similarly, we have coined the term health debt as a metaphor from the economic domain that refers to health behaviours postponed in favour of some momentary satisfaction. For example:

- No practice of physical exercises: avoiding physical exercises gives more time for other activities that do not burn energy. However, this behaviour does not help in maintaining the body’s aerobic and anaerobic conditioning, resulting, for example, in future cardiovascular problems.
- Fast food consumption: this is a practical and tasty type of food. However, fast foods are commonly high in saturated fat, which increases the cholesterol level, and overloaded with sodium, which raises the body’s blood pressure. The combination of these two aspects increases, for example, the probability of cardiovascular accidents.
- Smoking: nicotine causes the brain to release adrenaline, creating a slight sensation of pleasure and energy. However, the accumulation of nicotine damages the airways and the small air sacs (alveoli) found in the lungs.
- No sleep at the times aligned with the body natural cycle: some individuals, for example, play games up late at night (or early morning). While games are a form of momentary pleasure, this continuous behaviour disrupts the body’s circadian rhythm, which is connected to metabolism and weight by controlling the regulation of blood sugar and cholesterol. Circadian rhythms also influence mental health, including the risk of psychiatric illnesses (e.g., depression and bipolar disorder) and neurodegenerative diseases like dementia [15].

As with any other type of debt, early payments of especially small health debts are easier to accomplish. For example, if someone smokes for six months and modifies such behaviour (stop smoking), the lungs can recover by themselves. However, the damage from six years of smoking is harder to recover and requires extra effort. Therefore, health debt can be used to manage and communicate long-term consequences that unhealthy behaviours may cause. The two main scientific challenges for characterising health debt are measuring it and identifying the effort required to pay it. In the context of our study, and considering its behavioural perspective, we define health debt as follows:

Health debt is the difference between a usual average daily life behaviour and the minimal behaviour change that someone must adopt to obtain a healthy status in the time scale of interest.

The *healthy status* in this definition depends on the application domain and the timescale of interest. For example, suppose the application intends to monitor the health debt regarding obesity. In this case, the body mass index (BMI) values, defined by World Health Organisation (WHO), could be used to indicate such a healthy status. This particular value is a slow changing value, and assessment and management can span from months to years. This definition of health debt

gives an order of magnitude about the effort required in terms of behaviour change. Consider the following notation that supports our definitions:

- β_i : represents a behaviour at a specific time i . The constant n indicates the maximum value for i . For example, if a model works with a temporal window of seven values, then $n = 7$ and β_n is the last behaviour observed (this means $i = n$).
- $\beta_{i,j}$: as behaviour is a dense multifeatured concept, the previous notation can be extended with the index j that indicates a behaviour feature (e.g., distance travelled). The constant w indicates the maximum number of features. For example, if we $w = 4$, the model has $j \in [1.0.4]$ representing four different features.

Based on this notation, consider now the following example (Fig. 1).

In this example, $\beta_1.. \beta_n$ represents the longitudinal sequence of behaviours that are producing a poor value for a health feature y . The sequence $\beta_{n+1}.. \beta_{n+m}$ are recommended behaviours toward a target value for the same health feature y . Moreover, each behaviour β is characterised by a total number of w features j , resulting in a representation that composes a 2D vector of behavioural features over time. Thus, two structures $V\beta$ and $V\beta'$ (Fig. 2) are created based on Fig. 1. Fig. 2 also shows an example of instantiation for $V\beta$, where $n = 4$ and $i \in [\text{Monday, Tuesday, Wednesday, Thursday}]$; and $w = 4$, where $j \in [\text{distance travelled, average heart rate, time spent in intense activities, steps count}]$. Thus, each feature has a stream of values over time, which can be represented as hours, weeks, months, or days as in this example.

Given the vector $V\mu(\beta)$, representing the average value μ for each feature j (Fig. 2), the health debt calculation is conducted by subtracting the vector $V\mu(\beta)$ of each line of $V\beta'$. The values of the resultant n -dimensional vector are then normalised, summed, and divided by the number of features (w). The result is a value that gives the scalar notion of the health debt (1).

$$\text{Healthdebt} = \frac{\text{sum}(|V\beta' - V\mu(\beta)|_{\text{normalized}})}{w} \quad (1)$$

This strategy to define health debt has three advantages. Firstly, this formulation allows the identification of the behavioural features that are the main responsible for the debt. Secondly, the effort required to change the behaviour is detailed in each of the features that characterise such a behaviour. Thirdly, the approach is flexible since it can represent cases that require a long sequence (high m value) of new behaviours to obtain the target health (e.g., a daily routine of physical exercises to lose weight over a month), or a very short ($m = 1$) sequence (e.g., behaviour change at the current day to obtain a better sleep duration in this day). The case example in Section 3 discusses this latter scenario.

From a pragmatic perspective, it is very complex to measure health debt as a variable that involves all aspects of human health. That means physical health, psychological health, social relationships, and environmental aspects of health. For example, Lee et al. [16] proposed an estimation model focused only on predicting health-related physical fitness (HRPF) levels of individuals. Similar to the concept of debt, their study intends to identify HRPF values that could support the definition of fitness training programs (recommendations). Therefore, health debt can be specialised to focus on a particular health domain. For example, health debt can be associated with stress (Health debt^{stress}), or a more general category such as mental state (Health debt^{mental-state}). Another example is sleep quality (Health debt^{sleep-quality}), or one of its constructors, such as sleep duration (Health debt^{sleep-duration}).

The World Health Organization brings an interesting discussion and instrument (WHOQOL [17]) regarding the analysis of quality of life (QoL) domains and subdomains, and their influence on human health. Thus, health debt could be measured for each quality of life domain or subdomain, indicating the behaviour changes that should be conducted to improve the health in such a domain.

Fig. 1. Schema to characterise health debt.

$$V\beta = \begin{pmatrix} \beta_{i,j} & \beta_{i+1,j} & \beta_{i+2,j} & \dots & \beta_{n,j} \\ \beta_{i,j+1} & \beta_{i+1,j+1} & \beta_{i+2,j+1} & \dots & \beta_{n,j+1} \\ \beta_{i,j+2} & \beta_{i+1,j+2} & \beta_{i+2,j+2} & \dots & \beta_{n,j+2} \\ \beta_{i,j+3} & \beta_{i+1,j+3} & \beta_{i+2,j+3} & \dots & \beta_{n,j+3} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \beta_{i,w} & \beta_{i+1,w} & \beta_{i+2,w} & \dots & \beta_{n,w} \end{pmatrix} \quad V\beta_{\text{example}} = \begin{pmatrix} \text{Monday} & \text{Tuesday} & \text{Wednesday} & \text{Thursday} \\ 4500 & 2000 & 3000 & 5000 \\ 90 & 85 & 90 & 100 \\ 0 & 0 & 30 & 30 \\ 6000 & 2800 & 4000 & 7000 \end{pmatrix} \begin{matrix} \text{distance travelled} \\ \text{average heart rate} \\ \text{time spent in} \\ \text{intense activity} \\ \text{steps count} \end{matrix}$$

$$V\mu(\beta) = \left[\mu(\beta_i) \quad \mu(\beta_{i+1}) \quad \mu(\beta_{i+2}) \quad \dots \quad \mu(\beta_n) \right]$$

$$V\beta' = \begin{pmatrix} \beta_{n+1,j} & \beta_{n+2,j} & \beta_{n+3,j} & \dots & \beta_{n+m,j} \\ \beta_{n+1,j+1} & \beta_{n+2,j+1} & \beta_{n+3,j+1} & \dots & \beta_{n+m,j+1} \\ \beta_{n+1,j+2} & \beta_{n+2,j+2} & \beta_{n+3,j+2} & \dots & \beta_{n+m,j+2} \\ \beta_{n+1,j+3} & \beta_{n+2,j+3} & \beta_{n+3,j+3} & \dots & \beta_{n+m,j+3} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \beta_{n+1,w} & \beta_{n+2,w} & \beta_{n+3,w} & \dots & \beta_{n+m,w} \end{pmatrix}$$

Fig. 2. Vectorial representation for physical activity behaviour and an example of instantiation where i is represented by days of week, and j for behaviour features (e.g., steps count).

2.3. Architecture

The measurement of health debt is linked to the recommendation of a behaviour change, in such way this behaviour can be compared to the average current daily life behaviour of an individual. Two premisses are essential in this discussion. Firstly, this recommendation must guide individuals for behaviour choice values indicated as healthy in the literature. For example, if the system is focused on sleep duration, the literature indicates a period between 7 and 9 h of sleep per day. Therefore, the system must be able to recommend related behaviour changes (e.g., avoid vigorous physical activity 90 min before bedtime) to help individuals to reach this goal. Secondly, it is especially important that recommendations do not dramatically change the average behaviour of individuals. Otherwise, such individuals will not engage or ever accept the recommendations. For example, we should not recommend a diet with daily salad-based meals for someone who does not eat salad and is a heavy meat eater.

The next schema (Fig. 3) illustrates our architectural proposal to provide behavioural recommendations. A set of w features characterises a behaviour β over time (from 1 to $n + m$), forming a 2-D vector. Moreover, each column β_i is associated with an output (prediction variable), forming a tuple $\langle \beta_i, y_i \rangle$. As the training process aims at creating a model that predicts the last output variable of the longitudinal sequence, it uses the tuple $\langle [\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_{n+m}], y_{n+m} \rangle$. Indeed, a set of such tuples compose the training dataset.

After being created, the predictive model works as an evaluator of the behaviour changes generated by the recommender. This process

follows the next steps. Firstly, possible behaviours are generated by the recommender (Fig. 3a). The hyperparameter m , where m greater than 0, indicates how many behaviours β_i must be generated to complete the matrix, where $[\beta_i, | n + 1 \leq i \leq n + m]$. This population of behaviours represents recommendations that are then evaluated (Fig. 3b) by the predictive model. This evaluation tests each matrix formed by concatenating the input behaviours (β_1 to β_n) and the generated behaviours (β_{n+1} to β_{n+m}), inducing a value for the prediction variable. These values are ranked (Fig. 3c) and returned to the recommender. This cycle of generating, evaluating, and ranking behaviours is repeated until the recommender returns the final recommendation (Fig. 3d). As discussed in this section, the recommender must balance the ranking of recommendations and the difference between the average and recommended behaviours (i.e., no dramatic changes). Section 3.8 shows how our approach ensures this balance.

3. Case example: sleep behavioural debt

3.1. Objective

Given the longitudinal (six days) behavioural description of an individual, this case example aims at recommending a behavioural pattern for the seventh day that improves the sleep duration of the individual on such a day (Fig. 4). Thus, the model for predicting this sleep duration is trained with sets of behavioural features that represent seven days. The behavioural description uses features that are passively assessed by means of wearable sensors. In this case, a smartwatch. The features are

Fig. 3. Architecture for recommendations.

Fig. 4. Case example in the sleep domain.

daily step count, daily distance travelled (meters), daily time spent in soft, moderate, and vigorous physical activities (seconds), and daily average heart rate (beats per minute). After that, we use the generated recommendation to calculate the individual's health debt^{sleep-duration}, and analyse the rationale of such recommendations against results from the literature.

3.2. Behavioural dataset

This case example relies on data from 30 healthy adult volunteers that used Withings smartwatches for up to nine months. These devices collect data about the number of steps, distance travelled, time spent in soft, moderate, and vigorous physical activities, heart rate, and sleep duration. These devices also provide other data not used in our study due to their low precision (e.g., sleep stages time). These continuous data were consolidated to represent their total or average daily values. For example, the total number of steps per day and the average heart rate of a day. Our prediction variable is sleep duration. The following graph (Fig. 5) shows the distribution of the volunteers' sleep duration values in three classes, which represent poor (less than 7 h), recommended (7 to 9 h), and oversleeping (more than 9 h) durations. We organised these daily samples in frames of seven days. Thus, the idea is to use the data from the first seven days to predict the sleep duration of the seventh day. Due to the high rate of missing data of four volunteers (they do not present any complete data sequence of seven days), only 26 volunteers were considered in our final experiments. The data used in this paper are publicly available and described in Yareta portal.¹

3.3. Data augmentation

Our experiment only employed daily samples that had data for all input features and sleep duration available. This means they do not present missing data. Thus, 612 day samples were removed from the original set of 7786. These numbers give an overall missing data rate of 7.86 %. We used the sliding window strategy, with a window size of seven days and a timestep of one day, to augment the number of samples, as exemplified in the following equations (2). In this schema, the left-hand side of the arrow represents the input data, while the right-hand side represents the target data.

$$x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6, x_7 \rightarrow \text{sleepduration}(x_7).$$

$$x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6, x_7, x_8 \rightarrow \text{sleepduration}(x_8).$$

$$x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6, x_7, x_8, x_9 \rightarrow \text{sleepduration}(x_9).$$

...

$$x_{n-6}, x_{n-5}, x_{n-4}, x_{n-3}, x_{n-2}, x_{n-1}, x_n \rightarrow \text{sleepduration}(x_n) \quad (2)$$

After applying this strategy for each user, we obtained 4019 longitudinal structures (samples) of continuous seven days, with a mean of 155 structures/volunteer and standard deviation of 112 (minimum = 6, maximum = 351). The histogram of the seventh night sleep duration value (prediction variable) of each structure is illustrated in the schema below (Fig. 6), which shows a non-normal distribution verified with the Shapiro-Wilk test of normality.

3.4. Dataset – Generic vs individual

The generic dataset described above, from now on DS_G, has the data of 26 volunteers. It intends to be a generic dataset to train a model that could be used for any person. Alternatively, datasets can be created at the level of the individuals. In other words, this type of dataset, from now on DS_I, only has data of the individual that will use the model generated with such data. This approach relies on the principles of personalised biomedical informatics [18], which considers design

requirements that improve the utility of personal health records for future diseases diagnosis and treatment personalisation. Previous papers, such as [19], compare the use of generic and individual datasets in terms of the generated models' performance. We intend to conduct the same type of analysis in our experiments.

3.5. Dataset – Partial data vs full data

The recommendation architecture (Fig. 3) does not use part of the dataset information (i.e., $y_1..y_{n+m-1}$) during the training process. To better illustrate the potential importance of this information, consider that the vector y has data about sleep duration. This means that for each daily behaviour β_i , the dataset has information about the sleep duration (y_i) of this day. Suppose a recommendation system aims to provide suggestions to improve the sleep duration at y_{n+m} . In this case, it is not hard to agree that the sleep duration of the previous days may represent valuable information for such a prediction task. Based on this discussion, our experiments use two different input configurations. The partial dataset configuration (from now on DS_P) receives the dataset as specified in Fig. 3 (partial information), while the full configuration (from now on DS_F) has two input branches that respectively receive the behaviour matrix and the vector $y_1..y_{n+m-1}$.

3.6. Deep learning architectures

One of the main aims of this project was to identify a deep learning architecture to generate the predictive model (Fig. 3). This architecture should be simple since this paper is part of a larger project that intends to embed a recommendation module, together with other modules for data privacy and context, into mHealth wearable devices (e.g., Smartwatches). Therefore, we considered the following architectures and hyperparameters adjusted via empirical experiments:

1. Vanilla LSTM: single hidden layer of LSTM units (50 units using relu activation function), and an output linear dense layer (1 unit, no activation) used to make the prediction.
2. Stacked LSTM: represents multiple hidden LSTM layers stacked one on top of another. Our experiments used only two LSTM layers, with the same configuration of the Vanilla LSTM, also followed by an output linear dense layer (1 unit, no activation) used to make the prediction.
3. Bidirectional LSTM: uses the vanilla LSTM as basis, but learning the input sequence both forward and backward, concatenating these two interpretations.
4. CNN-1D: uses two 1D convolution layers (filters = 64, kernel_size = 2, activation='relu'). This layer creates a convolution kernel that is convoluted along the temporal dimension to produce a tensor of outputs. The architecture is complemented with a 1-D max pooling (pool_size = 2), a Flatten, and a Dense layer.
5. CNN/LSTM: a CNN model can be used in a hybrid model with an LSTM backend where the CNN is used to interpret subsequences of input that are provided as a sequence to an LSTM model to interpret [20]. Thus, we configured this architecture using the CNN-1D and Vanilla LSTM.
6. Temporal Pattern Attention (TPA) [21]: relies on the attention mechanism [7], which permits the architecture to utilize the most relevant parts of the input sequence by a weighted combination of all the input vectors, with the most relevant vectors being attributed the highest weights [21].

This attention-based approach (TPA) was particularly included since it demonstrated a high performance compared to other recent similar attention-based strategies, as discussed in [21].

¹ <https://yareta.unige.ch/home/detail/19bf7f3c-7d07-48be-8c03-9f754f766906>.

Fig. 5. Distribution of the sleep duration values into three classes for each volunteer (Vi).

Fig. 6. Histogram with the distribution of the 4019 nights regarding the sleep duration in seconds.

3.7. Evaluation – DL models for sleep duration prediction

We randomly split the data (set of seven days) into training and validation sets using a rate of 80/20 %. The training process was performed using a batch size of 8 during 50 epochs or until the learning saturated. The model compiler was configured using the Adagrad optimizer with a learning rate of 0.01 %, mean squared error as loss function, and the root mean squared error (RMSE) as validation metric. We captured the loss curves for training and validation to observe the evolution of the accuracy and possible overfitting problems. Results present the average and standard deviation of 10 runtimes. We adjusted these hyperparameters via empirical experiments.

3.8. Evaluation – Sleep duration recommender

As illustrated in Fig. 4, the idea of the predictive model is to receive a computationally generated behaviour and evaluate the effect of such behaviour on the outcome prediction variable (e.g., sleep duration). As a set of six features composes this behaviour, and each of these features is a continuous numeric value, we decided to use a genetic algorithm (GA) to generate patterns that lead the prediction variable toward the best, or

approximately best, possible value. Our GA version creates an initial population of randomly generated behaviours (candidate solutions). The prediction module evaluates these behaviours and calculates their fitness value. The fitness value of a behaviour is the numeric value that determines how good such behaviour is as a factor to improve the health aspect represented by the prediction variable. This value is represented by $Fitness(\beta^g)$, where β^g is the generated behaviour, and its range is domain dependent.

The following schema (Fig. 7) illustrates an example with five behaviours (chromosomes). Each chromosome in this schema comprises six features (genes), representing the optimization parameters, and has a fitness value returned by the prediction module.

Our GA implementation uses a chromosome with six genes, one for each behaviour feature, such as in Fig. 7. However, using a population of 20 chromosomes. We used the single point as the mating approach (genes after a single point are replaced with the genes of the other parent to create two offsprings), and employed the combination of two selection methods and two mutation methods, described as follows:

- Fitness half selection: half of the candidate solutions with the highest fitness values are used to generate the new population [22].

Chromosomes							
	Gene1	Gene2	Gene3	Gene4	Gene5	Gene6	Fitness
$\beta^{g.1}$	9046	7056	47461	4347	0	79	6.0
$\beta^{g.2}$	6337	4957	49680	2220	0	81	7.5
$\beta^{g.3}$	6538	5130	40200	1080	1740	81	5.6
$\beta^{g.4}$	7109	5492	38280	1561	0	73	7.0
$\beta^{g.5}$	4383	3414	35160	300	0	79	9.0

Fig. 7. Representation of behaviours as chromosomes.

- Roulette wheel selection: fitness values are used to choose candidates where the best chromosome stands a higher chance of selection [22].
- Reset mutation: one or more genes are randomly replaced using values also randomly generated within the valid range for such genes [23].
- Gauss mutation: one or more genes are randomly replaced with a value generated according to the Gauss distribution around the original genes [23].

The interaction between GA parameters and methods is usually nonlinear. Thus, they cannot be individually optimized. Moreover, there are no conclusive results on what the best set should be used since this definition also depends on the domain. Thus, finding appropriate control parameters is a time-demanding task. The parameters and methods used in our research were empirically adjusted considering 50 iterations since we did not obtain significant gains after that. Therefore, the process stops after 50 iterations or when the fitness value is higher than the minimal healthy constant (e.g., 7 for sleep duration). This later condition is in accordance with the health debt definition, since the problem is not to find the best behaviour change, but the minimal behaviour change that guides the individual to a healthy condition.

After that, we started the second round of experiments, using, at this time, the Gauss distribution to constrain the generation of the initial population and control its mutation. The idea was to avoid the generation of behaviours that are not close to the average behaviour of individuals. Therefore, we maintained a standard deviation of 0.01 for the generation of the initial set of behaviours (population). This deviation allows that 95.5 % of the behaviours' features stay inside of the following intervals: steps ± 700 , distance travelled ± 0.6 (km), time spent in soft activities ± 0.42 (h), time spent in moderate activities ± 0.11 (h), time spent in vigorous activities ± 0.4 (h), and heart rate ± 40 (beats per minute). We examined different values for the following mutation hyperparameters:

- Standard deviation of mutation (γ): controls the Gauss distribution for the generation of new genes when mutations occur. Genes that become negative during the mutation have their values set to zero. The experiments use the values 0.01 and 0.001.
- Mutation rate (α): indicates how many genes (features) may be modified. The experiments use 1 and 2 as values.

Finally, the health debt analysis considers the recommended behaviours that produce a healthy prediction (e.g., sleep duration between 7 and 9) to calculate the health debt using equation (1). Lower results indicate the minimal behaviour change that the respective individual should perform. We also conduct a qualitative discussion of the resultant health debt as part of our analysis.

Table 1

Summary of the results for sleep duration prediction, emphasising the best result.

DL Architecture	Dataset aspects		MSRE	
			Train	Validation
Vanilla LSTM	DS_G	DS_P	1.461 \pm 0.01	1.438 \pm 0.05
		DS_F	1.395 \pm 0.01	1.437 \pm 0.04
	DS_I	DS_P	1.107 \pm 0.02	1.110 \pm 0.09
		DS_F	1.121 \pm 0.01	1.090 \pm 0.06
Stacked LSTM	DS_G	DS_P	1.473 \pm 0.01	1.455 \pm 0.01
		DS_F	1.397 \pm 0.02	1.430 \pm 0.06
	DS_I	DS_P	1.136 \pm 0.02	1.041 \pm 0.04
		DS_F	1.161 \pm 0.02	1.105 \pm 0.05
Bidirectional LSTM	DS_G	DS_P	1.435 \pm 0.01	1.490 \pm 0.01
		DS_F	1.410 \pm 0.02	1.365 \pm 0.02
	DS_I	DS_P	1.070 \pm 0.01	1.158 \pm 0.07
		DS_F	1.141 \pm 0.01	1.156 \pm 0.12
CNN-1D	DS_G	DS_P	1.448 \pm 0.05	1.473 \pm 0.02
		DS_F	1.395 \pm 0.05	1.366 \pm 0.03
	DS_I	DS_P	1.050 \pm 0.02	1.353 \pm 0.07
		DS_F	1.079 \pm 0.02	1.204 \pm 0.21
CNN/LSTM	DS_G	DS_P	1.479 \pm 0.02	1.518 \pm 0.04
		DS_F	1.397 \pm 0.06	1.418 \pm 0.04
	DS_I	DS_P	1.122 \pm 0.04	1.136 \pm 0.24
		DS_F	1.100 \pm 0.03	1.308 \pm 0.18
TPA – Temporal Pattern Attention	DS_G	DS_P	1.458 \pm 0.01	1.462 \pm 0.02
		DS_F	1.395 \pm 0.02	1.389 \pm 0.07
	DS_I	DS_P	1.036 \pm 0.07	1.138 \pm 0.10
		DS_F	1.001 \pm 0.03	1.020 \pm 0.08

4. Results

4.1. Evaluation of DL architectures

Table 1 summarises the results obtained from our experiments, regarding the prediction of sleep duration, which use a combination of the DL architectures and dataset aspects: generic (DS_G) vs individual (DS_I) and partial (DS_P) vs full (DS_F). The evaluation returns the MSRE for training and validation.

The obtained results indicated that:

- Using the DS_I and DS_F approaches, the temporal pattern attention obtained the most apparent results. However, the difference to other approaches, such as stacked LSTM, is not so significant.
- Independent of the approach, the MSRE value is still high for this problem since the aim is to identify a value in the interval of 1 to 15. A probable reason is the low quality of the assessed data since they were collected *in the wild* and consequently are very noisy (e.g., volunteers with daily steps count lower than 400).
- The results show that the prediction is more accurate when the architecture uses the individual dataset (DS_I). This conclusion is valid for all DL architectures.
- The DS_F strategy is always more accurate when the DS_G strategy is used. However, we cannot extend this conclusion for DS_I since DS_P presented more accurate results for the Stacked LSTM and CNN-1D architectures.

Given these results, we decided to use the model generated with the TPA approach, together with the DS_I and DS_F strategies, as the fitness function of the recommendation module.

Table 2
Example of recommendations for four volunteers using the prediction model as the fitness function.

Selection	Mutation	Vi	Outcomes		
			Behaviour recommendation*	Sleep duration (h)	
Fittest half	Reset	V1	[69, 2.7, 15.7, 1.0, 8.5, 115]	5.4 → 7.7	
		V2	[31590, 23.7, 7.2, 4.8, 6.3, 110]	5.4 → 7.2	
		V3	[69, 0.06, 0.75, 2.0, 1.6, 119]	5.8 → 7.9	
		V4	[31590, 0.06, 9.68, 0.8, 3.8, 115]	3.4 → 7.5	
	Gauss	V1	[3221, 21, 1, 15, 0.11, 0.81, 115]	5.4 → 7.7	
		V2	[31590, 21, 2.4, 5.65, 8.9, 71]	5.4 → 7.2	
		V3	[9225, 0.06, 2.69, 1.9, 0.4, 108]	5.8 → 7.6	
		V4	[25286, 0.06, 6.4, 4.6, 0.8, 109]	3.4 → 7.4	
		Reset	V1	[69, 0.06, 16, 1.3, 9.9, 102]	5.4 → 7.7
			V2	[31590, 26.3, 2.4, 4.96, 8.9, 105]	5.4 → 7.2
			V3	[69, 0.06, 2.7, 0.46, 5.7, 96]	5.8 → 7.6
			V4	[28438, 0.06, 14.5, 0.3, 1.8, 113]	3.4 → 7.5
Gauss	V1	[3221, 2.7, 15.34, 0.11, 7.9, 118]	5.4 → 7.7		
	V2	[28438, 23.7, 8.69, 5.5, 3.0, 115]	5.4 → 7.2		
	V3	[69, 2.68, 1.07, 0.8, 3.6, 77]	5.8 → 7.6		
	V4	[31590, 15.8, 8.0, 5.2, 3.0, 120]	3.4 → 7.4		

*The behaviour vector for each volunteer (vi) is composed of six elements: steps (integer value), distance (km), time spend in soft (hours), moderate (hours), and vigorous (hours) activities, and heart rate (beat per minute).

4.2. Recommendations

Table 2 summarises the recommendations for behaviour changes generated by the genetic algorithm, using the temporal pattern attention-based model (DS_I and DS_F) as the fitness function.

We selected the four volunteers (V1 to V4) with the highest amount of longitudinal data. Then, we selected specific days of their data that presented a short sleep duration. For example, 5.4 h for V1 and V2. The aim was to generate behaviours that could increase the sleep duration of such volunteers. The results show that, independent of the selection and mutation strategies, the outcomes converge to the same or similar value. For example, V1 (7.7), V2 (7.2), V3 (7.6 and 7.9), and V4 (7.4 and 7.5). These values are between 7 and 9 h, which are the recommended sleep duration. However, this approach has a strong limitation since it generates recommendations that are not feasible. For example, a high number of steps (e.g., 31590) or daily rate heart average (115), meaning the person should spend most of the time being in physical activity state.

Considering this limitation, we modified the algorithm to constraint the generated values to a range inside a Gauss distribution, as discussed in Section 3.8. The results are presented in Table 3 for different values of α and γ .

Our intention in using these two hyperparameters (α and γ) was to gradually increase the search space of the algorithm and, consequently the variance of the generated genes. Table 3 shows that the behaviours are feasible and close to the average behaviours of the volunteers. In some cases (V2), however, the recommender is not able to find a suitable, healthy solution (between 7 and 9). Then, we tried to increase the value of γ to 0.05 and 0.1 to expand the search space. The results using $\alpha = 2$ were:

- $\gamma = 0.05$: [16677, 23.7, 0.1, 2.9, 12.1, 114], 5.4 → 6.6
- $\gamma = 0.1$: [6373, 28.9, 1.7, 5.8, 2.0, 114], 5.4 → 6.7

These values show that the recommender cannot return a value inside the target interval even when the search space is increased. Moreover, the behavioural features already present unfeasible values, such as a distance travelled of 24.6 km. This result is interesting because it emphasises that the search for a healthy status may depend on longer behaviour changes. Thus, this particular case may require behavioural modifications within two or three days (Fig. 3, $m = 2$ or 3) rather than only in the current day ($m = 1$).

Table 3
Recommendations using the prediction model and constraints on population changing.

Vi	α	γ	Outcomes	
			Behaviour recommendation*	Fitness
V1	1	0.001	[5301, 2.7, 4.0, 0.36, 0, 83]	5.4 → 7.5
		0.01	[3221, 2.7, 5.0, 0.53, 0, 82]	5.4 → 7.6
		0.001	[5743, 2.7, 3.8, 0.36, 0, 82]	5.4 → 7.5
	2	0.01	[6373, 2.7, 5.0, 0.5, 0, 89]	5.4 → 7.6
		0.001	[4734, 2.7, 1.7, 0.58, 0.34, 89]	5.4 → 6.0
		0.01	[6373, 5.3, 1.7, 0.2, 0, 89]	5.4 → 6.0
V2	1	0.001	[6373, 3.7, 1.7, 0.2, 0, 89]	5.4 → 6.0
		0.01	[6373, 5.3, 1.7, 0, 0, 89]	5.4 → 6.0
		0.001	[5365, 2.3, 0.6, 0.9, 72]	5.8 → 7.8
	2	0.01	[5175, 5.4, 1.7, 0.62, 0.79, 69]	5.8 → 7.9
		0.001	[5365, 4.7, 2.6, 0.58, 0.77, 72]	5.8 → 7.9
		0.01	[4923, 4.9, 1.7, 0.58, 0.77, 69]	5.8 → 7.9
V3	1	0.001	[9525, 6.49, 1.7, 0.58, 0, 67]	3.4 → 7.5
		0.01	[9525, 6.49, 1.7, 0.58, 0, 67]	3.4 → 7.5
		0.001	[9525, 7.9, 1.7, 0.6, 0.68]	3.4 → 7.5
	2	0.01	[6367, 7.9, 1.7, 0.58, 0, 72]	3.4 → 7.5

*The behaviour vector for each volunteer (vi) is composed of six elements: steps (integer value), distance (km), time spend in soft (hours), moderate (hours), and vigorous (hours) activities, and heart rate (beat per minute).

Table 4
Health Debt (HD) results.

Vi	Behaviours		HD
	Average	Recommended	
V1	[5834, 4, 3.73, 0.49, 0, 82]	[5743, 2.7, 3.8, 0.36, 0, 82]	0.01
V3	[5393, 5.12, 2.5, 0.64, 0.8, 68]	[5365, 4.7, 2.6, 0.6, 0.8, 72]	0.01
V4	[7358, 6.5, 1.52, 0.9, 0.04, 65]	[9525, 7.9, 1.7, 0.6, 0, 68]	0.04

4.3. Health debt measurement and analysis

Table 4 presents the average behaviour for three volunteers and the calculated health debt (HD), considering the recommendations obtained with $\alpha = 1$ and $\gamma = 0.01$ (Table 3), and the equation (1). V2 was not considered since the recommender could not return a proper recommendation (fitness value ≥ 7).

These results show that V1 and V3 have low HD values and their recommendations indicate they only need to maintain a behaviour similar to their average. V4 has a higher HD, and her recommendation indicates that she needs to mainly increase her level of activities (e.g., walking more). Regarding this result, the following graphs (Fig. 8) show that the recommendations for V1 (similar to V3) and V4 lead the

travelled distance toward values around the historical average of the individuals (6 to 8 Km). These values are also the daily recommendations of the physical health literature [24].

This result also corroborates the literature findings, which say that moderate physical activities, such as walking or jogging, seem more effective than vigorous activity in improving sleep duration, regardless of the individuals' age [25]. The results support this affirmation since the recommended behaviours do not significantly modify the values of the time spent in vigorous activities (the fifth element in the vectors). In such a type of analysis, the system acts as a resource to support explanations of how different kinds of behaviours could affect the sleep duration of individuals. In this case, for example, the recommendations show that the distance travelled tends to be an essential feature to improving sleep duration.

5. Discussion

The results discussed in [26] indicate that the health systems' ability to explain their reasoning is critical to users' acceptance of their decisions. The design of a health debt notion considers this need since it clarifies features' contributions and how they can be combined to obtain

Fig. 8. Graphical representation of travelled distance over a 7-days period.

feasible recommendations. Therefore, health debt is a strategy for explaining recommendations in a way that makes its reasoning more transparent, contributing to users' acceptance of such recommendations.

The practical experiments were important to emphasise some implementation aspects. For example, the use of individual rather than general datasets produces more accurate models. Moreover, the use of constraints on the variability of behaviours features generates more feasible recommendations. We also confirmed some results from the literature. For example, according to [25], moderate physical activities, such as walking or jogging, seem more effective than vigorous activities in improving sleep duration, regardless of the individuals' age. Thus, the recommendations are in accordance with the literature findings, showing that the distance travelled tends to be an essential feature of the sleep duration analysis.

The current version of the system returns a "raw" version of recommendations. This means numeric values for heart rate, number of steps, and others. However, simply delivering all these raw values together can confuse rather than assist final users. For example, a recommendation can indicate the decrease in steps count and, simultaneously, the increase in the travelled distance. Thus, such a recommendation initially seems to be in conflict. Our current idea is to build an interface module that can receive and interpret the features of this raw recommendation, generating a simple recommendation in natural language. Thus, the interpretation of the previous example (decrease of steps count and increase of the travelled distance) could generate a recommendation for jogging or running (more distance travelled with fewer steps). Another example, the increase heart rate and decrease in distance travelled may indicate that users should carry out anaerobic exercises. Such a topic is an interesting research direction that could be conducted with the assistance of Exercise Physiologists, which study the body's responses to physical activity as well as how the body adapts to physical activity over time. Additionally, the context definition is also important since recommendations could be unsuitable for the current context of individuals. This means contexts potentially influence the set of behaviours that could be or not modifiable.

Regarding the architectural design, the temporal pattern attention obtained a slightly better accuracy than the other approaches. This is an interesting result since the attention mechanism was designed to mainly keep up with context and content when sequences are too long, avoiding the vanishing gradient problem. However, our experiments showed that the attention mechanism is also adequate for processing short data sequences. The experiments also emphasised that the use of the Gauss function as initialisation and mutation operators are the main configurable aspect of genetic algorithms associated with generating feasible recommendations.

The main limitation of our study is the dataset's quality, which is very noisy and presents some non-realistic values. Our analysis of other datasets shows that this phenomenon usually occurs when data are assessed *in the wild* via wearable devices. Indeed, volunteers do not use their devices all the time. Moreover, technical problems generate very low or high values that affect the fitness function. The process of binning continuous features into categories can attenuate this problem. Categories are amply used in the health domain since they facilitate the discovery and interpretation of patterns, which are difficult to analyse otherwise. On the other hand, binning leads to loss of information. The definition of the number of categories for each feature is an open and essential issue in this approach [27].

Finally, due to the complexity of the problem, this work provides several opportunities for extensions. For example, as previously discussed, the recommendations are given in a "raw" format. In pragmatic implementations, they should be interpreted and transformed into natural language sentences. We are also only considering $m = 1$ (Fig. 4). This means recommendations for one-time point. More complex scenarios certainly will require recommendations for long periods.

6. Conclusions

Human behaviour is an inherently complex longitudinal multi-featured subject matter that directly impacts the health of individuals. Thus, the intelligent generation of behaviour change recommendations can be an important resource to avoid or attenuate health issues. This paper presents a strategy that uses the analysis of recommendations to characterise and measure the health debt of individuals regarding a particular physiological, physical, or mental state. As a case example, we focused on the sleep domain. However, the methodology presented in this paper can be similarly used to cover any other health domain. The main requirement is the existence of data that support the generation of accurate models.

Our research directions aim to quantify the evolution of health debt over time. A new dataset, which contains larger and more diverse data (e.g., psychological), is also in analysis. It will allow, for example, the characterisation of other relationships between sleep duration and mental/social features, which could better explain the reasons for prediction variable values.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Clairton Siebra: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Data curation. **Lais Amorim:** Software, Validation. **Jonyserg P. Quintino:** Project administration. **Andre L.M. Santos:** Conceptualization, Methodology. **Fabio Q.B. da Silva:** Conceptualization, Methodology. **Katarzyna Wac:** Supervision, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbi.2022.104277>.

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